

THE EMERGENCE OF THE COMPETENCE APPROACH IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND ITS IMPORTANCE TODAY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the essence of the concept of competence, the emergence of the competence approach in education and the stages of its development, the application of the competence approach to the educational process, and the importance of developing students' competencies in a specific field.*

Keywords: *speech, competence, speech competence, speech components, gradual development, education, educational process.*

INTRODUCTION

On the basis of comprehensive economic reforms carried out in any country, first of all, further improvement of the education system and types remains one of the most important and urgent issues. From this point of view, the confessions of President Sh.Mirziyoyev, who said: "If you ask me what is bothering you, I will answer that it is the education and training of our children"[5], which is at the heart of every reform implemented in our country today. shows that the future of the growing young generation lies in the issue of their maturity and bright prospects [9].

The development of the country, its achievement of high indicators in all spheres lies directly in the attention paid to education in this society and the issue of reforms implemented. It is not a secret to any of us that science is the main force that brings society to a high level of development.

Today, in order to raise general secondary education to a new stage of development, to train competitive personnel who can lead from national recovery to national progress to sustainable development, taking into account the requirements of advanced national and foreign experiences and international assessment programs, the tasks of improving the curriculum, teaching methodology and educational quality assessment system were determined.

From this point of view, new views, a new approach, new thoughts and opinions are emerging regarding the study of the teaching experience of foreign countries and its application to the content of education.

MAIN PART

Robert Carlos said that elementary school should do more than just teach reading, writing, and counting. Because stimulating the intellectual activity of each child during the formative period, as well as developing his natural abilities, is very important for his further success [2]. In fact, the issue of education is a process that constantly adapts to the requirements of the times and improves in harmony with scientific and technical achievements. In particular, the issue of improving the primary education system and preparing students for life processes as independent thinkers expresses the goal of raising a mature generation who can feel responsibility for their future and the development of society. From this point of view, it is permissible to dwell on the

concept of "competence", which is increasingly important in the content of education today. Because in recent years, new approaches such as communicative approach, integrated approach, competence approach are being applied to language education.

At the root of the application of the concept of competence to the content of education lies a new approach to the education system, the issue of development of the education system, of course. In accordance with the requirements of the present time, it is not enough to give students only scientific-theoretical knowledge, but also to expand the children's worldview, to make them mature as a person who can independently observe and apply the acquired knowledge to everyday life. Emphasis was placed on incorporating the concepts of "competence" into the content of the main goal of each lesson.

The introduction of the competence problem into the field of education and the history of its development can be conditionally divided into four stages:

The 1st stage (1960-1970) – Introduction and use of the term "Competence";

The 2nd stage (1970-1990) – Formation of different views on competence;

The 3rd stage (1990-2000) – The period of application of competence and competence as a category to education;

The 4th stage (from 2000 to the present) is related to the inclusion of the competence approach in the content of the standards of professional and general education subjects [6].

The concept of competence was first mentioned in scientific literature in the 1950s and 1960s. American scientist N. Chomsky in his works "Syntactic Structures", "Aspects of the Theory of Syntax" compares the concepts of "competence" and "performance" and compares the differences in the content of these terms with the knowledge of the "speaker-listener" in the communication and communication of the language. reveals the differences between its use in activities and interprets competence as a person's ability to perform an activity [3].

The requirements of modern education, in particular, "dynamic changes in the labor market, the increase in the requirements for not only knowledge and skills, but also personal qualities of a person" created the need to organize education based on the competence approach, and several scientists called the competence approach based educational problems were studied and scientific-methodical foundations were developed [8].

By the second and third stages of the development of the concept of competence, the concepts of "competence", "competence", "competence approach" were observed by scientists in different ways. In particular, in the opinion of M.M. Vahabov, "education based on a competency-based approach is an education aimed at forming the competencies of students to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in their personal professional and social activities"[8].

F. Delamare and J. Winterson describe competence as standard behavior, behavior required by a certain activity, competence as the level of compliance with this requirement, that is, the final result of demonstrating competence [8].

Also, G.A. Asilova summarized the definitions of the concepts of "competence" and "competence" in her dissertation work, "competence" is the effective application of personal qualities and knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of working in a certain field. "competency" defines that it is an existing and possible ability to perform a specific activity [1].

According to B. Kh. Khodzhayev, "competency serves to integrate the student's efforts to master new personal experience and self-development"[10].

Education based on the competence approach is characterized by the preparation of students to use the acquired information in standard and non-standard situations of educational and life activities. Based on the study of international experiences, attention was paid to the introduction of education based on the competence approach in our country, and as a result, in accordance with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No.187 dated April 6, 2017, students through each academic subject The State Education Standard has been developed, which describes in detail the basic and subject-related competencies to be acquired. These changes indicate the high attention paid to education in our country today.

Based on the analysis of scientific literature and the above-mentioned points, it should be noted that the main essence of teaching based on the competence approach is to use the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired by students during their personal life, as well as in the future orientation to the formation of competencies to be used in professional and social activities. In order for students to engage in personal, social, economic and professional relationships in their future life, to take their place in society, to solve the problems encountered in this process, and most importantly to be competitive in their field and profession. must have the necessary basic competencies [7].

CONCLUSION

President Sh. Mirziyoyev said: "If we pay attention to the realization of the abilities of our children from childhood and mobilize all our opportunities for their development, many more Berunis, Ibn Sinas, and Ulugbeks will grow up in our country" [4].

In fact, the realization of great people of the future begins today, because the development of the country is inextricably dependent on what kind of person the youth will become in the future. Further reform of the primary education system, which is the foundation of our children's future, is one of the priority tasks in this regard. It is known that through the educational process, general secondary schools are responsible for providing students with basic competencies, including communication, the ability to work with information, self-development as a person, socially active citizenship, general cultural, mathematical literacy, to be aware of science and technology news and to form the competences of use [6]. In carrying out this process, first of all, the teacher must have professional competence at the level of the position he holds. Only then he can successfully organize the pedagogical process. Such qualities as professional knowledge, honesty, truthfulness, inquisitiveness, tireless productive work, creativity and creativity elevate him. There is no doubt that a pedagogue can develop mature individuals with high spirituality and deep thinking through such qualities.

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